

Synthetic studies and structural aspects of metallacyclic derivatives of tin(IV) : Better precursors for SnO₂

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Abstract : Tin complexes of the type [(acac)₂Sn(OPrⁱ)_{2-n}(OCH₂CH₂OR)_n], (where n = 1–2; R = Me, Et and Buⁿ) were synthesized by treating bis(acetylacetonato)diisopropoxytin(IV) with alkoxy alkanols in appropriate molar ratios. All these reactions have been carried out in refluxing benzene under anhydrous conditions to yield mononuclear derivatives and isolated by evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure. On the basis of elemental analysis, IR and NMR (¹H and ¹³C) spectral studies, a *cis* octahedral geometry around Sn^{IV} is proposed. These derivatives have proven their worth to produce tin dioxide at low temperature by sol-gel technology.

Keywords : Bis(acetylacetonato)diisopropoxytin(IV), alkoxy alkanols, elemental analyses.

Introduction

A very few tin(IV) alkoxy complexes have been characteristically reported in recent years. Though, a considerable work has been documented on tin tetra isopropoxide along-with analogues new derivatives during the decade of 1990¹. The role of β-diketonato ligands in the coordination sphere of tin complexes increases the stabilization of the precursors towards hydrolysis reaction; moreover, it induces the feasibility for the preparation of stable sols and gels with higher hydrolysis ratio². Though, different methods have been employed to synthesize metal oxide nano materials, but chemical vapor deposition is also a well-accepted technique to produce crystalline, phase pure materials with controlled microstructure and morphology of tin(IV) oxide from these metallo organic derivatives³ due to their low boiling and decomposition temperature. Possessing a wide band gap, tin dioxide (SnO₂) ceramic displays higher infrared reflectance, high visible light transmittance, in LED devices, transparent electrode, electronic devices such as electro-chromic, electro-luminescent, photovoltaic, gas sensors, resistor, heater and coat-

ing for an optical absorbent as well as anode materials for Li-ion batteries^{4,5}. Therefore, in view of above-said quite fascinating applications, we are describing herewith, the synthesis of new precursors from bis(acetylacetonato)-diisopropoxytin(IV) and characterization of these metal complexes are also discussed in detail.

Experimental

All reactions were performed in moisture free environment and the chemicals were of analytical grade and made anhydrous before use. [(acac)₂Sn(OPrⁱ)₂] was prepared as reported in literature⁶. Tin⁷ and isopropanol⁸ have also been estimated according to well established methods. Infrared spectra were recorded as Nujol mulls on Nicolet Magna-550 spectrophotometer. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained from 90 MHz JEOL FX 90Q spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference in CDCl₃. Elemental analysis of the complexes were recorded on Elementar Vario EL III instrument.

Preparation of [(acac)₂Sn(OPrⁱ)(OCH₂CH₂OMe)] : Benzene solution (~20 mL) of [(acac)₂Sn(OPrⁱ)₂]

1.22 g (2.79 mmol) was added to another solution of benzene (~20 mL) and HOCH₂CH₂OMe 0.22 g (2.89 mmol) and the contents were refluxed for ~5 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by the estimation of liberated isopropanol obtained in the azeotrope along with benzene iodometrically. After completion of the reaction, an orange colored solution was obtained followed by removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, furnished (97%) an orange-red viscous liquid product. Other remaining complexes were also prepared by applying the similar route and the details are summarized in Table 1.

(q, CH), 1.25 (t, CH₃), 3.46–3.73 (m, all CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 26.32, 26.66 (CH₃), 103.53 (CH), 191.27, 187.77 (CO), 25.82 (CH₃), 64.12, 24.72 (CH₃), 64.20 (OCH₂CH₃), 64.25 (OCH₂CH₂OEt), 72.30 (OCH₂CH₂OEt); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : (C-O, OPrⁱ) 1010, (Sn-O) 448, (C-O) 1060 and (C-O-C) 1060; Anal. Calcd. : C, 43.33; H, 7.70; O, 23.77%. Found : C, 43.24; H, 7.67; O, 23.71%.

Complex 4 : Yield 98%; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 2.0–2.08 (CH₃), 5.56 (CH), 1.22 (t, CH₃), 3.42–3.68

Table 1. Synthetic and analytical data of Sn^{IV} complexes

Sl. No.	Reactants (g) (a) [(acac) ₂ Sn(OPr ⁱ) ₂] (b) HOCH ₂ CH ₂ OR	Molar ratio	Complex	Pr ⁱ OH (g) Found (Calcd.)	Sn (%) Found (Calcd.)	OPr ⁱ (%) Found (Calcd.)
1.	(a) 1.22, (b) R = Me, 0.22	1 : 1	[(acac) ₂ Sn(OPr ⁱ)(OCH ₂ CH ₂ OMe)]	0.15 (0.17)	26.2 (26.3)	12.9 (13.1)
2.	(a) 1.09, (b) R = Me, 0.38	1 : 2	[(acac) ₂ Sn(OCH ₂ CH ₂ OMe) ₂]	0.29 (0.30)	25.5 (25.4)	–
3.	(a) 1.06, (b) R = Et, 0.22	1 : 1	[(acac) ₂ Sn(OPr ⁱ)(OCH ₂ CH ₂ OEt)]	0.14 (0.15)	25.3 (25.5)	12.4 (13.7)
4.	(a) 0.91, (b) R = Et, 0.38	1 : 2	[(acac) ₂ Sn(OCH ₂ CH ₂ OEt) ₂]	0.24 (0.25)	23.8 (23.9)	–
5.	(a) 1.22, (b) R = Bu ⁿ , 0.31	1 : 1	[(acac) ₂ Sn(OPr ⁱ)(OCH ₂ CH ₂ OBu ⁿ)]	0.14 (0.15)	23.9 (24.1)	11.6 (11.9)
6.	(a) 1.04, (b) R = Bu ⁿ , 0.57	1 : 2	[(acac) ₂ Sn(OCH ₂ CH ₂ OBu ⁿ) ₂]	0.28 (0.29)	21.3 (21.5)	–

NMR, IR and other details of the synthesized metal complexes :

Complex 1 : Yield 97%; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 2.03–2.14 (CH₃), 5.54 (CH), 1.14 (t, CH₃), 4.32–4.78 (q, CH), 3.43 (s, OCH₃), 3.55–3.72 (m, all CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 26.34, 26.85 (CH₃), 103.52 (CH), 191.24, 187.64 (CO), 25.87 (CH₃), 64.08 (CH), 58.72 (CH₃), 64.24 (OCH₂), 71.35 (OCH₂CH₂OMe); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : (C-O, OPrⁱ) 1050, (Sn-O) 445, (C-O) 1080 and (C-O-C) 1050; Anal. Calcd. : C, 42.04; H, 7.50; O, 24.50%. Found : C, 42.11; H, 7.46; O, 24.48%.

Complex 2 : Yield 99%; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 2.05–2.12 (CH₃), 5.58 (CH), 3.38 (s, OCH₃), 3.50–3.61 (m, all CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 26.37, 26.78 (CH₃), 104.58 (CH), 191.28, 187.72 (CO), 58.25 (CH₃), 64.26 (OCH₂), 71.34 (OCH₂CH₂OMe); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : (Sn-O) 450, (C-O) 1090 and (C-O-C) 1055; Anal. Calcd. : C, 40.62; H, 7.24; O, 27.05%. Found : C, 40.59; H, 7.18; O, 27.01%.

Complex 3 : Yield 97%; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 2.02–2.12 (CH₃), 5.70 (CH), 1.22 (t, CH₃), 4.30–4.72

(m, all CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 26.34, 26.82 (CH₃), 103.72 (CH), 191.32, 187.68 (CO), 24.74 (CH₃), 64.18 (OCH₂CH₃), 64.20 (OCH₂CH₂OEt), 72.20 (OCH₂CH₂OEt); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : (Sn-O) 445, (C-O) 1070 and ν(C-O-C) 1035; Anal. Calcd. : C, 43.14; H, 7.64; O, 25.54%. Found : C, 43.09; H, 7.59; O, 25.51%.

Complex 5 : Yield 97%; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 2.04–2.12 (CH₃), 5.52 (CH), 1.18 (t, CH₃), 4.38–4.65 (q, CH), 1.19 (t, CH₃), 3.43–3.70 (m, all CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 26.38, 26.77 (CH₃), 103.88 (CH), 191.24, 187.48 (CO), 25.77 (CH₃), 64.03 (CH), 15.34 (CH₃), 64.36 (OCH₂Pr), 40.70 (OCH₂CH₂Et), 25.13 (OCH₂CH₂CH₂Me), 64.40 (OCH₂CH₂OEt), 72.32 (OCH₂CH₂OBu); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : (C-O, OPrⁱ) 1015, (Sn-O) 450, (C-O) 1085 and (C-O-C) 1030; Anal. Calcd. : C, 45.71; H, 8.08; O, 22.43%. Found : C, 45.67; H, 8.01; O, 22.39%.

Complex 6 : Yield 98%; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 2.03–2.10 (CH₃), 5.50 (CH), 1.16 (t, CH₃), 3.45–3.78 (m, all CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 26.36, 26.76 (CH₃), 103.98 (CH), 191.28, 187.29 (CO), 15.38 (CH₃),

64.32 (OCH₂Pr), 40.76 (OCH₂CH₂Et), 25.18 (OCH₂-CH₂CH₂Me), 64.35 (OCH₂CH₂OEt), 72.35 (OCH₂CH₂OBu); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : (Sn-O) 450, (C-O) 1080 and (C-O-C) 1020; Anal. Calcd. : C, 47.41; H, 8.32; O, 22.97%. Found : C, 47.38; H, 8.29; O, 22.93%.

Results and discussion

To make a proper comparison, complementary reactions of the precursor [(acac)₂Sn(OPrⁱ)₂] with three alkoxy alkanols have been carried out in refluxing anhydrous benzene in suitable stoichiometry as depicted below :

[where LH = HOCH₂CH₂OR; R = Me, Et, Buⁿ; n = 1–2]

All these reactions are quite facile and quantitative in yields. The liberated isopropanol was estimated oxidimetrically until the distillate showed its absence. The traces of solvent was then concentrated under reduced pressure for 4 h. The obtained products are orange-red viscous liquids, soluble in organic solvents like benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride etc.

IR spectra :

IR spectra of these compounds show strong bands at 1580–1595 and 1500–1520 cm⁻¹ (1680 cm⁻¹ in free acetyl acetone) due to ν(C-O) and ν(C-C) stretching vibrations, respectively. The shifts of the carbonyl stretching vibrations in the complexes towards lower frequencies suggest a bidentate chelating nature of the acetylacetonate moieties. A broad band due to ν(OH) present in the spectra of free ligands (at ca. 3400 cm⁻¹) disappears in all of complexes, indicating the deprotonation of the ligands moiety and the formation of a Sn-O bond. The ν(Sn-O) band appears in the 445–450 cm⁻¹ region^{9–11}. The ν(C-O) and ν(C-O-C) stretching frequencies of the alkoxy alkanolate⁹ moiety appear at 1090–1060 and 1060–1020 cm⁻¹, respectively.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR chemical shifts of these compounds exhibit distinct absorption peaks and the resonances of hydroxyl protons for free ligands were not absorbed. It indicates deprotonation of -OH group and the formation of Sn-O bond. Characteristic signals have been observed in

the ¹H NMR spectra of all these complexes at δ 1.94–2.04 and 2.02–2.14 and 5.40–5.70 ppm for methyl and methene of acetylacetonate moieties, respectively. The presence of two discrete and equivalent resonances associated with the CH₃ of the acetylacetonate is consistent with a *cis* configuration for the acetylacetonate moieties^{9–11}.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR spectra of the tin complexes showed no significant shift in the positions of alkoxy carbon of these ligand moieties, further suggests that the alkoxy alkanolate is bound to tin atom in monodentate fashion. Double peaks of CH₃ (26.32–26.38 and 26.66–26.82) and CO (191.22–191.32 and 187.29–187.77) of acetylacetonate moieties confirm the *cis* configuration of these derivatives^{9–11}. Alkoxy alkanolate carbons are observed at expected positions.

On the studies of the above significant spectral data, the plausible and tentative structure has been proposed in Fig. 1 for these new derivatives :

Fig. 1. Proposed structures for [(acac)₂Sn(OPrⁱ)_{2-n}(OCH₂CH₂OR)_n]. (where n = 1–2; L₁ = OPrⁱ/OCH₂CH₂OR; L₂ = OCH₂CH₂OR; R = Me, Et and Buⁿ)

Conclusion

On the basis of the NMR (¹H and ¹³C) spectral studies, IR and elemental analysis, a *cis* octahedral geometry of these tin complexes has been proposed for the afore-mentioned new complexes. The work does not stop here. Sincere efforts are in the progress to get and characterize the nano structured tin dioxide from these newly synthesized metallo-organic derivatives of tin(IV).

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References

1. D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra, I. P. Rothwell and A. Singh, "Alkoxo and Aryloxo Derivatives of Metals", Academic Press, San Diego, USA, 2001.
2. M. Verdenelli, S. Parola, L. G. Hubert-Pfalzgraf and S. Lecocq, *Polyhedron*, 2000, **19**, 2069.
3. I. Barbul, A. L. Johnson, G. Kociok-Kohn, K. C. Molloy, C. Silvestru and A. L. Sudlow, *Chem. Plus. Chem.*, 2013, **78**, 866.
4. M. Okuya, S. Kaneko, K. Hiroshima, I. Yagi and K. Murakami, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2001, **21**, 2099.
5. A. L. Dawar and J. C. Joshi, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1984, **19**, 1.
6. D. Chandler, G. D. Fallon, A. J. Koplick and B. O. West, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1987, **40**, 1427.
7. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 5th ed., Wiley, London, 1989.
8. B. Samuel, T. Kiran, V. G. Prasanth and M. Pathak, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2014, **23**, 699.
9. M. Pathak, R. Bohra and R. C. Mehrotra, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2003, **28**, 187.
10. M. Pathak, B. Samuel, T. Kiran, V. G. Prasanth, R. Bohra and K. J. Kim, *Adv. Mater. Res.*, 2012, **584**, 411.
11. M. Pathak, B. Samuel, T. Kiran, V. G. Prasanth, K. Sivasankar, R. Bohra and K. J. Kim, *Adv. Mater. Res.*, 2012, **584**, 415.